

The role of motivation in second language learning process in adolescents

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Abstract

This study aims at providing an outlook on the motivational factors that play an idealistic role on the development of procedures of second language learning and also on the factors which most adroitly influence the learners understanding of second language. The study was conducted on the students of a private university studying English language at their post graduate level. The study was conducted quantitatively and the results are compiled in the form of diagrams and graphs. The results conclude that intrinsic motivation plays a more significant role than the extrinsic motivation. The role of teacher in inducing motivation among students is indisputable. Media also works to enhance the motivational levels of students and students themselves feel that they learn English language more efficiently using media sources, hence it should be incorporated in language learning classes in a well-organized way.

Keywords Motivation, factors of motivation, teacher's role, language learning, media in language learning

1. Introduction

The word Motivation has been derived from Latin word “movera” which means “to move” (Dorneyi 2013). Motivation is an inevitable element behind the success of every person, in every vista of life. In the process of foreign or second language learning motivation plays a very vital role and many studies have been performed to support this statement. Dorneyi (2003) described motivation as “willingness, effort and attitudes towards language learning”. Gardner proposed a motivation theory which states that motivation includes three elements. One is effort (to learn a language) other is desire (to accomplish that goal) and the last one is positive effect (to enjoy that task).

Gilankjoni, Leong and Saburi (2012) discussed that the success of any person's action depends upon the intensity of desires of a person and his struggle or extent of his attempts to achieve that goal. It is the impulse that triggers the action. In the case of second language learning, motivation is not only the attempt but it is a desire to achieve the goal of language learning. It is not true that a person making effort does essentially contain the motivation too, but it is true that a motivated person is not only focused but also extends his efforts towards the goal and is finally succeeded. (Gardner 1985). Teachers teaching second language should be aware of the importance of motivation, so that at any stage in language learning he/she could make the students learn the language efficiently by evoking their motivation. Huitt (2001) stated that if the learners lack intrinsic motivation,

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motivation can be elicited in them by drawing their attention towards the importance of language.

Pardee (1990) declared motivation to be a sort of encouragement for a person to take the action or to develop an indication towards the achievement of their goal. The role of teacher can never be ignored in evoking the motivation of students. The personality of teacher, the methodology she uses in language learning environment actually plays a dramatic role in raising their motivational levels. Brown (2012) noticed that good language teachers are those who can serve as a model of good use of target language, can understand student's needs, has a caring attitude and use methods which are culturally and socially appropriate. A research was performed by Mr. Naw Sant in Thailand (2018). In his research while assessing the factors that play an important role in promoting motivation in language learning classrooms, he concluded that teachers are very good motivators in English language learning classrooms and know well how to employ different teaching methods which are inspiring and meet students different needs and interests.

The instrumental motivation is a kind of motivation that refers to learning language for a pragmatic or practical reason for instance for the growth of career or getting a monitorial award. Integrative motivation is a kind of motivation that refers to learning of language for the purpose of acquiring the knowledge of culture of a particular community. These two terms were introduced by Robert Gardner. Studies of Gardner showed that integrative motivation is more significant in language learning than the instrumental motivation in second language learning. However, many recent studies hold that instrumental motivation could be more important. Dornyei (1990) observed instrumental motivation to play a significant role in second language learning. Brown (2000) suggested that the motivation among students is generally a combination of both of these kinds. He gave example of international students studying and residing in U.S. These students learn English language for both academic function and for the purpose of integrating with the people and culture of that country. Dornyei stated that motivation changes over time (2001). Someone may be triggered by instrumental motivation but this motivation may then transform into integrative motivation with the passage of time and vice versa. William and Burden also claim, that motivation in language learning is an outcome of both the external and internal influences which drives the learner to accomplish their goals of learning.

1.1. Purpose

The purpose of this study is to figure out the factors that play an important role in inducing motivation for language learning among students. This study also aims to provide a deep insight into how an individual's ability to learn a second language could be enhanced by the external environment that could result in building a framework for their internal motivation. Teachers play a vital role in provoking their motivation, how teachers can work in order to equip them with the motivation that is required to learn a language, is the main focus of this study. These days' media can also be used to learn a language through movies, news and other sources, but how

much these factors influence the learner's ability to learn a language, to empower them with the motivation for language learning which is the actual essence of language learning.

1.2. Research Objectives

The main objectives of this study are

- 1-to find out how motivation helps a learner learn a second language,
- 2-to figure out the role of teachers in provoking the motivational levels of students,
- 3-to determine the role of media in eliciting motivation for language learning among students.

1.3. Significance of Study

Motivation is an ineluctable feature for attaining success in every realm of life whether that is second language learning or acquiring any kind of expertise in life. This study aims to focus on the factors that can work best for inducing motivation among students to learn a second language.

Students around the world still face a lot of hurdles in learning second language whether they do belong to a culture where it is extensively being used. This study will help students to be consistent in language learning by finding ways to improve their motivational levels that will help them in acquiring language in a better way, assisting them with their self-motivation.

This study is also beneficial for teachers. It may provide them with materials, methods and techniques that can be used to induce motivation in students. It provides teachers with an opportunity to have an insight into their own teaching methods and thrust them with the ideas of improving their methods and techniques they use to keep students motivated. As the data has been collected from the students, it may help teachers to bring a change in their attitudes which eventually can work better for making students self-motivated and may help them building strong interaction between them.

This study could also help parents who are worried about their children's laziness and lack of motivation in language learning for some outward goal like settling abroad or gaining desirable job. It could help them with the ideas they may use to enkindle motivation for learning of language.

1.4. Limitations

This study focuses on the factors that best play an important role in kindling the motivation among students for language learning. This study was conducted on a limited number of students studying English language at University of Lahore, Pakistan. The students were of MPhil level, which were taken as participants of this research.

1.5. Research gap

Many studies have been performed in order to bring forth the importance of motivation in second language learning process but none of them discussed the issues that could hinder the process of learning second language at University level, with regard to what students think could help them learning language practically. The previously done researches did not

address the role which media could play in language learning process with respect to adult students' perspective.

1.6. Literature review

The views of researchers vary depending upon to what kind of and what factors they found to be more influencing ones. Lucas (2010) found that learners are intrinsically motivated for developing reading and speaking skills. Dital (2012) found that learners are highly motivated both instrumentally and interactively for acquiring English language and both of these kinds of motivation are essential in language learning. He claimed that learners learning procedure is not influenced by external factors.

A study was conducted by Neol et al (1990) about the relationship between the student's motivation and teacher's manner of communication. The purpose of this study was to conclude the relation between the teacher's attitude to support the learning environment and the student's progress in learning a language. He came up with conclusion that teacher's communicative style had strong association with the intrinsic motivation among students.

Similarly, many studies were conducted for the association between intrinsic motivation and reward for language learning.

Gardner and Macintyre (1991) conducted a study in which two pairs of 46 students each were taken. One group was offered a reward of \$ 10 if they become successful in passing a vocabulary task of a language, and the other group was just asked to perform their best and no reward was offered to them. The result favored intrinsic motivation because the group which was given a reward proved to be more prepared group, they spent more time learning the vocabulary as compared to the other group. A study was carried out by Muchnick and Wolfe (1982) which tried to highlight the importance of instrumental and integrative motivation in foreign language learning. The students who were learning Spanish language in high schools of U.S were taken into consideration. These total number of 337 students proved that a combination of both instrumental & integrative motivation is more profitable in second language learning.

Dornyei (1994) concluded in his research that these are many other elements that work best for elucidating motivation among students the teacher's manner, strategies and the methodologies which she implies to treat the students play a vital role. He also concluded there are many other elements that are related to course, like syllabus, materials and interaction of students with their peers plays a significant role in eliciting motivation. Ushiuda (1996) pointed out in his research that cooperative and collaborative study of students for the purposes language learning proves to be more lucrative because they learn through interactive and experience of one another. A research study was conducted by Ahmed m al Ghamdi (2014) he came up with conclusions the both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation are rooted somehow deep inside and individuals themselves should be aware of motivation that many help them with the learning process.

William and Burden (1997) gave suggestions to the teachers regarding the idea of eliciting motivation in students for language learning. They suggested that teacher should help the students in achieving their goal of

language learning. They should be provided with reasons and benefits of learning second language the teacher should work to create a safe on non-threatening environment in class and assist the students to develop intrinsic motivation.

2. Methodology

2.1. Theoretical framework

R. C. Gardner formulated a socio educational model theory in 1997, which suggested that there are two important factors that influence the learning of a second language in learners. These two factors are ability and motivation. He proposed that individual's social back ground also plays a very significant role in the learning of language. He claimed that learner learns a second language in two contexts. One is formal which accounts for the proper educational context. The other is informal which holds the social context as an important stimulus for learning. Formal learning occurs through involvement of educational institution and classroom environment whereas the informal learning of language occurs through the usage of television and radio, even social media is playing a very vital role in language learning. The researcher proposed a questionnaire which contains enquiries regarding their motivation and ability. For the learning process to occur learners should contain higher levels of both the ability and motivation. Ability and motivation both are required in formal context of learning whereas mere motivation can work alone for informal learning procedures.

He also proposed a quantitative questionnaire for the measurement of ability and the extent of motivation also the factors that work best for inducing motivation in individuals for language learning process. This measurement tool is called as AMTB or Attitude Motivation Test Battery, which carries options for individual degree of agreement and disagreement.

2.2. Sampling and Population

For the purpose of this study 20 students who were studying English language in University of Lahore, Pakistan were taken into consideration. These were students of language at MPhil level and were generally in their 1st or 2nd semester. The criterion for respondents of this study was that they had to be mentally sound to respond and willing to participate.

2.3. Data Collection

Data was collected in the form of answers through a questionnaire that contained questions regarding their ability and motivation that affects their learning procedure more whether intrinsic or extrinsic. It also carried questions regarding the factors that work best for eliciting their motivational levels. The questionnaire was provided to students during the class time. It contained 11 questions which were further brought to quantitative analysis.

2.4. Data analysis and tools

The survey for this study was performed in University of Lahore and the answers were gathered from the students of English language. It was performed by students who were willing to participate in the survey. The data collected through the questionnaire was analyzed and classified

according to the interests of students and the parameters set by the researcher. The data was expressed in the form of descriptive pie diagrams and graphs by using coding and content analysis technique using simple computerized tool called as Microsoft Office. The quantitative method was used.

3. Findings

The question regarding intrinsic motivation was posed to students. As Figure 1 demonstrates, 40% of the students responded that they speak English language because they personally like speaking it.

Figure 1. Intrinsic motivation for learning English

Of all the students, 30% of them thought that it makes them feel confident about themselves while 20% responded they speak it because it is an international language whereas only 10% thought they use English language to impress others.

Figure 2. General reasons for learning English

Students were asked the reason which motivates them to learn English language. Sixty percent of them answered that they learn it for a better job, 25% answered that they are bound to learn it. 10% of the students replied they are learning it because they want to settle abroad and only 5% of them thought they learn to impress others.

Figure 3. The reason to improve English

A comparative question was posed to the participants to analyze their source of motivation. 40% of respondents answered that they want to improve their language proficiency because they personally like speaking it, 15% claimed

that they learn English language for getting a better job; 20% said that they learn it because it makes them feel confident; 10% said it to be a need of time, and 5% replied that they want to improve because they want to settle abroad and nobody said that they learn it to impress other people.

Figure 4. Teachers as motivators

Students were asked to respond regarding role of teacher as a motivator. 60% of students suggested that teacher can provide motivation by giving a friendly and non-threatening environment in class; 20% of them thought that teacher should design the methods and techniques consulting with students; 15% of them suggested that teacher should do counseling personally, and only 5% of them gave idea of offering a reward. No one holds the opinion that they should punish the students to get required results.

Figure 5. The techniques to be used

When students were asked to select the best technique out of many techniques which teachers should employ to induce motivation for better learning, 50% of students marked that teachers should make students

interact efficiently in order to induce motivation for learning; 30% of them suggested that media or prop should be introduced by her in the classroom; 10% of the students selected providing a non-threatening environment could be a better option, and 10% of the students responded that teacher should only work as a demonstrator.

Figure 6. Feeling nervous by learners

To enquire for the extent to which they feel nervous while speaking English, 40% of them strongly disagreed with the statement, 25% moderately disagreed, 15% of students slightly agreed, 5% of students strongly disagreed, and 15% moderately agreed.

Figure 7. The reason for learners feel nervous

When the reason for being nervous was enquired, 50% of students believed they feel shy because it is not our native language, 15% of students believed that they have a fear of being mocked, 15% of them claimed that they have

not been taught properly, and 15% of them thought they feel shy because they personally do not like speaking it and again 10% of them thought that they feel shy because they believed they have a poor knowledge of it.

Figure 8. The tools used to improve English

When the participants were asked the question inquiring the tools they use to improve their English, 40% of students claimed that they watch English movies, listen to songs and news in English which help them learn the language, 20% of them claimed that they learn English best from their parents, 30% of the students stated that they learn English by reading novels and books, and 10% said that they learn English through English learning apps in their phones.

Figure 9. The use of media to learn English

When they were asked to give their opinions regarding the extent to which they agree with the statement that media can be used to learn English language, 80% of them strongly agreed with the statement that media can be used for learning language and inducing motivation in them, 10% of students moderately agreed and 10% of them moderately disagreed with the statement.

Figure 10. The most useful aspect of media in learning English

When they were asked about the specific aspects of media they use to improve their English language, 60% of them replied that they learn English language best from English movies songs, 20% of them claimed that they learn through News channels whereas only 10% of them responded that they learn through websites, Facebook, Instagram and same number of population believed that they learn through apps that are used for vocabulary and pronunciation.

Figure 11. The factors motivating to enhance English speaking abilities

When the question inquiring the factors effecting the learning of English was asked to the students, 40% of them responded that they learn English through media, 30% of them thought that teachers are best source 20% of

them suggested that teaching materials and syllabus matters more to them, and, 10% responded that their families help them in learning language.

4. Discussion

This study was performed regarding the impact of motivation on student's learning of second language and the factors that play a significant role in inducing motivation among them. Data was collected from students studying English language at a private university and Gardner's theory of motivation was applied to it which states that an individual's learning of second language is affected by two factors which are ability and motivation. Through a survey it is concluded that language learning caters both intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation, but results concludes that intrinsic motivation plays a more prominent role among individuals learning a second language. Most of the students responded that they learn second language because they have a personal liking for it or they feel confident while speaking. While responding about extrinsic factors they claimed that they learn language for the purpose of getting a better job. Some of them also replied that they learn for any outward reward or prize. Some had an idea that they learn because they are bound to learn English language for it a demand of our educational institution. A few students also learn English language for it being an international language. At a comparative edge almost 80% of students learn language out of their own personal liking for this language.

Role of teacher is also of immense importance and cannot be neglected. Information regarding student's ideas pertaining to the strategies which can be used by a teacher to evoke motivation among students, almost most of them had an idea that teacher should work best for providing a non-threatening environment or a student friendly environment. A teacher should also perform as a personal counselor to resolve the issues of students which are creating obstacles in language learning process. Teacher could also offer a reward to make them indulge in the learning process. Techniques which a teacher could employ for ensuring better learning of students includes developing a healthy interaction among students and promoting the use of media and props in class. Students laid stress upon the idea of providing a fearless environment of class which could eradicate the barriers that may restrict learning of second language and impart them with ample confidence necessary for language learning. Students also have negative associations with learning of second language. They feel shy or nervous while speaking English language the most important reason is that it is not their native language.

One of the most important tools which can be used to improve English language in students is media. Students learn a lot through English movies and English songs, it is an easiest way to gather the knowledge while having entertainment. Most of the students claim that they learn a lot of language while watching movies and listening to English music and news channels. It enhances their knowledge of vocabulary and often helps them with the correct usage of tense and grammar. Students also acquire language by reading books but since the use of media has reached to its apex these days, students find it easier to learn language through media as websites, apps on

play store and many other sources are also being used extensively which makes language understanding easy and available at a touch of finger. This kind of learning though informal can provide a better source to students who have intrinsic motivation.

Students, according to the survey consider two factors of paramount importance, which can prove to be excellent sources of motivation. These two factors are role of teacher and use of media. Teachers can also prove to be a role model for students if they provide a non-threatening and friendly environment of class along with providing a stimulus for motivation necessary for language learning. Teachers can also incorporate media in their classes and can make the language learning a better and enjoyable experience.

5. Conclusions

Motivation is regarded as a crucial element for the successful learning of second language. Gardner laid emphasis on the factors of ability and motivation for language learning process to occur. Intrinsic motivation is more of paramount importance than extrinsic one. As it all comes from within, it has more influential impact on learner's ability to learn a second language. Teacher's role in eliciting motivation of students cannot be ignored. Teachers should work their best to provide a compassionate environment for class and play a role of benevolent counselor to understand and provide solutions to problems that may hinder the learning process. Media is also playing a vital role in making students capable of acquiring second language by developing their positive attitudes towards language learning. Media can be used with collaborative techniques to evoke motivation in students during class activities.

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